

JUVENILE DELINQUENCY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS IN ISEYIN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OYO STATE**OLAKOJO, Olayide Amos**

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Abstract

Juvenile delinquency has been observed to be a pressing social issue affecting secondary school students in many parts of Nigeria, including Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State. Thus, this study investigated the factors responsible for this source. The specific objective was to examine the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency and the moderating influence of gender, school location and teaching experience of teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State. A descriptive design was adopted for this study. The population of this study comprised all teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria which is estimated 679,592. However, simple random sampling technique was used to select 400 respondents out of the 679,592. The instrument used was a researcher-designed questionnaire entitled "Factors Responsible for Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (FRJDQ)". The instrument has reliability co-efficient of 0.79 after being subjected to the test -re-test method. The hypotheses were analyzed with t-test and Analysis of Variance statistics. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. The findings of this study revealed that the most factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State were social and economic factors, family background and peer influence. There is a significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State based on gender. However, there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students based on school's location and years of teaching experience. The study, therefore, recommended that there should be seminar for parents, teachers and school administrators on how they can reduce the level of juvenile delinquency, irrespective of the years of teaching experience, gender and school location.

Keywords: Juvenile Delinquency, Secondary Schools, Teaching experience, Family background, Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State

Introduction

Juvenile delinquency has emerged as a pressing social issue affecting secondary school students in many parts of Nigeria, including Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State. It is the behaviour that violates societal norms and laws, such as truancy, vandalism, theft, drug abuse and violent conduct among youths. Adolescents, who are in a critical stage of physical, emotional, and social development, are particularly susceptible to engaging in delinquent behaviours due to a range of environmental,

familial, and individual factors. The prevalence of such behaviours disrupts the academic and moral development of students and poses significant challenges for teachers, parents, and policymakers in the region. Understanding the specific causes and dynamics of juvenile delinquency in Iseyin is vital to addressing its root causes and mitigating its adverse effects on education and societal stability.

Juvenile delinquency in Nigeria refers to the involvement of young people, typically those between the ages of 10 and 18, in

criminal or antisocial behaviour. This phenomenon has been a growing concern, particularly in urban areas where poverty, unemployment, peer pressure, and a lack of adequate social and educational opportunities exacerbate the likelihood of youth engaging in criminal activities. Juvenile delinquency encompasses a range of offenses including theft, drug abuse, sexual offenses, violence, and gang-related activities (Ogundele, 2020; Dada, 2021). One of the key drivers of this issue is the breakdown of family structures, which often leaves youths without proper guidance and supervision, increasing their vulnerability to negative influences. Additionally, the lack of rehabilitation programmes and the overburdened judicial system often result in juveniles being subjected to punitive measures rather than corrective or restorative approaches (Adewale & Okunola, 2020). In response to this challenge, the Nigerian government and civil society organizations have implemented several programs aimed at addressing juvenile delinquency, such as juvenile detention centers and counseling services, though their effectiveness remains inconsistent due to resource constraints and insufficient funding (Ogunyemi, 2019). A significant shift towards addressing the root causes of juvenile delinquency, such as socio-economic factors, family instability, and lack of education, has been proposed by experts who argue for a more holistic approach to juvenile justice that includes prevention, rehabilitation, and reintegration into society (Dada, 2021). Moreover, with the rise of social media and online platforms, cybercrime has become an increasingly prevalent form of juvenile delinquency; further complicating efforts to combat youth crime in the digital age (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2022).

Review of Related Literature

Juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Nigeria has become an increasing concern for educators, parents, and policymakers, as it has serious implications for both the individuals involved and the broader society. Secondary school students, typically aged between 10 and 18 years, are particularly vulnerable to delinquent behaviour due to the developmental challenges of adolescence, including identity

formation, peer pressure, and a desire for social acceptance (Akpan & Udo, 2020). Common offenses among delinquent students include truancy, bullying, substance abuse, theft, physical violence, and sometimes sexual assault (Ogunlade, 2018). Various socio-economic factors contribute to these behaviors, including poverty, family instability, and limited access to quality education, which often result in a lack of discipline and supervision at home (Adeyemi, 2019). Peer influence is a major factor in this age group, as students are more likely to engage in delinquent acts when they are encouraged or pressured by friends or classmates (Bamidele & Folarin, 2021). Additionally, the rising prevalence of cyberbullying and internet fraud among students, largely fueled by easy access to smartphones and social media, is an emerging form of delinquency that complicates the situation (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2022). While schools have implemented disciplinary measures such as suspensions and expulsions, these approaches are often reactive rather than preventive. Scholars advocate for a more comprehensive approach to addressing juvenile delinquency, which includes counseling programmes, mentorship, parental involvement, and community-based initiatives aimed at addressing the root causes of delinquency and providing students with positive outlets for expression and development (Ogunlade & Olayemi, 2021). In the light of the complexity of juvenile delinquency in Nigerian secondary schools, there is an urgent need for more robust policies and intervention strategies that focus on prevention, early intervention, and rehabilitation rather than punitive measures alone.

Statement of the Problem

The need to conduct a research study on the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State is rooted in the increasing prevalence of deviant behaviours that disrupt academic environments and societal norms. Juvenile delinquency poses significant challenges to educational institutions as it impacts not only the academic performance of affected students but also the overall learning

environment. By identifying the specific factors contributing to such behaviors, this research can help educators and policymakers design targeted interventions to curb delinquency and foster a more conducive learning atmosphere.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to find out factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State. The study sought to examine whether the moderating variables of gender, school location and years of teaching experience would influence the respondents' expression on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What are the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated to guide the conduct of this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on gender
2. There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students on Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State based on school location
3. There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State based on years of teaching experience.

Significance of the Study

School administrators would benefit from the findings as it would provide them with detailed insights into the root causes of juvenile delinquency in their schools.

Teachers, being at the forefront of students' interaction, will benefit from the study by gaining a deeper understanding of the behavioral patterns and triggers of juvenile delinquency. This knowledge can help them identify at-risk students early and apply effective classroom management strategies. With proper guidance, they can establish better teacher-student relationships and create inclusive learning environments that deter delinquent behaviours. The study's findings can be disseminated to teachers through professional development sessions, handbooks, or training workshops conducted in collaboration with the local education board. The study would benefit students directly by fostering an improved school environment that supports positive behavior and personal growth.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. It investigated moderating variables of gender, school location, and years of teaching. This study was limited to primary school teachers in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State. Descriptive research design was adopted for the study and it covered the entire Iseyin local government area, Oyo State.

Methodology

Design

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey. Descriptive survey research employs questionnaire in order to determine the opinion, attitudes, preference and perception of people's interest to the researcher. In view of this, the researcher therefore considered descriptive survey method most appropriate for this study.

Population, Sample and Sampling Procedures

The population for this study comprised 679,592 teachers in Oyo State (Oyo State Ministry of Education, 2024). The target population for this study consisted of primary school teachers in Iseyin LGA. According to the Research Advisor sample size determination table (2006), the sample size of 383 was recommended for a population size of this

study at 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. However, the researcher increased the sample size by 5% (19 respondents) which gave a total of 402. The addition of 19 more respondents was done in order to cater for attrition. In selecting the sample for the study the multi stage sampling procedure was adopted which comprised of proportional and random sampling techniques.

At stage one, simple random sampling technique was used to select six communities which comprise: Osoogun, Ado-Awaye, Adegbola, Aba-Tapa and Aborisade in Iseyin respectively. This was considered in order to give equal chance of sample selection to all the senatorial districts.

At stage two, random sampling technique was used to select the sample of 402 primary school teachers in Iseyin local government schools.

Instrumentation

Instrumentation is a process of developing measuring devices and methods for collecting data in educational researches. The instrument that was used in collecting data for this study is a questionnaire tagged "Factors Responsible for Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (FRJDQ)". Questionnaire has been known to be one of the most common and effective research instruments to elicit useful information. The questionnaire was designed personally by the researcher. The questionnaire has three sections. Section A dealt with demographic data, that is, personal information of the respondents. It consisted of three variables of respondents' which are gender, school location and years of teaching experience. Sections B dealt with items that elicited information on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. The respondents were to indicate their responses using four-point Likert-Type rating scale of; Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Psychometric Properties of the Instrument:

Validity: In order to ensure content validity of the instrument on this study, the instrument was given to 5 experts in the Department of Educational Psychology, Oyo State College of

Education, for content validity. Suggestions and modifications made were incorporated into what constitute the final version of the instrument.

Reliability: Reliability has to do with consistency and stability of an instrument. Reliability is the consistency, accuracy, stability and trustworthiness of a measuring instrument or score obtained. That is, how far the instrument would give the same score on different occasions or with different set of equivalent items under the same condition. Test-retest method was used on the same set of 20 primary school teachers in Ibarapa east local government within an interval of two weeks to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The two sets of scores obtained were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and coefficient of 0.79 was obtained.

Procedure for Administration of the Instrument and Data Collection

The questionnaires were administered to the selected respondents in the selected schools by the researcher with the help of two trained research assistants. Personal administration enabled the researcher to establish rapport which in turn motivated the teachers to cooperate. The researcher collected the questionnaire on the spot after the items have been completed to minimize loss.

Procedure for Scoring the Instrument

The questionnaire items were scored based on the format of each of the sections. Section 'A' was scored and analysed statistically using percentage while sections B with 20 items on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students were scored using four-point Likert-type rating scale as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points
 Agree (A) = 3 points
 Disagree (D) = 2 points
 Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point

The modality that was used in determining factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students was through the mean scores. Since the highest and the lowest possible scores are 4 and 1 respectively, the average mean is 2.50

($4+3+2+1 = 10/4$). Hence, scores from 2.50 and above were regarded as high factors rate while below 2.50 were regarded as low factor rate. However, a mean average was used to determine the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students. On the factors responsible, any item having mean score of 2.50 and above was regarded as factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers while below 2.50 was not counted as factors responsible for juvenile delinquency..

The data for this study was subjected to appropriate statistical analysis. Percentage was used to analyse the data obtained from demographic section while mean score was used to answer research question. The Independent t-test and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were inferential techniques used for testing of significant difference, involving the variables. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

This section covers demographic data using frequency counts and percentages.

Method of Data Analysis

Table 1: The distributions of respondents on variables:

Item	Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	187	46.7
	Female	213	53.3
	Total	400	100.0
School Location	Rural	170	42.5
	sub-rural	55	13.7
	Urban	175	43.8
	Total	400	100.0
Teaching Experience	1-5 years	115	28.7
	6-10 years	165	41.3
	11 years and above	120	30.0
	Total	400	100.0

Table 1 above indicates that 187 (46.7%) respondents were male while 213 (53.3%) were female; for school location, 170 (42.5%) were from rural location, 55 (13.7%) were from sub-rural while 175 (43.8%) were urban; for teaching experience, 115 (28.7%) were 1- 5 years, 165 (41.3%) of the respondents were from 6-10 years, while 120 (30.0%) were from 11 years and above. This implies that females with 213 (53.3%) respondents were more than male respondents; urban respondents with 175(43.8%) were more than others. It also revealed 6-10 years of teaching experience were more than others.

Research Question 1: What are the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Table 2: Means and Rank order analysis on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State.

S/N		Mean score	Rank
	Family Background		
1	Parental neglect contributes to juvenile delinquency.	2.60	
2	Frequent parental conflicts lead students to engage in delinquent behaviour.	2.71	
3	Lack of proper parental guidance increases the likelihood of delinquent acts among students.	2.95	
4	Students from broken homes are more prone to delinquency.	2.72	
5	Economic hardship in the family influences students to engage in delinquent acts.	2.74	
	Family Background	2.74	
	Peer Influence		
6	Peer pressure encourages secondary school students to engage in delinquent behaviours.	2.80	
7	Association with delinquent friends increases the likelihood of juvenile delinquency.	2.65	
8	Belonging to a gang or peer group affects students' behavior negatively.	2.59	
9	Students are likely to mimic delinquent behaviors they observe in their peers.	2.81	
10	Peer influence has a stronger impact on behavior than family influence among students.	2.75	
	Peer Influence	2.72	
	School Environment		
11	Poor supervision by teachers contributes to delinquent behaviors among students.	2.73	
12	Bullying and harassment in schools encourage delinquent tendencies.	2.77	
13	Lack of discipline policies in schools promotes delinquency among students.	2.70	
14	Academic failure or poor performance leads students to engage in delinquent acts.	2.62	
15	Overcrowded classrooms contribute to the rise of delinquent behaviours.	2.61	
	School Environment	2.686	
	Social and Economic Factors		
16	Exposure to violent content in the media encourages delinquent acts among students.	2.64	
17	The influence of social media increases students' tendency to engage in delinquency.	2.63	
18	Poverty in the community contributes to juvenile delinquency.	2.68	
19	The absence of youth recreational facilities encourages delinquency among students.	2.69	
20	A lack of role models in society leads students to engage in delinquent behaviours.	2.76	
	Social and Economic Factors	2.76	

Summary of the Table 2: factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State

S/N		Mean score	Rank
A	Family Background	2.744	2 nd
B	Peer Influence	2.720	3 rd
C	School Environment	2.686	4 th
D	Social and Economic Factors	2.76	1 st

Table 2 above revealed respondents based on the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. It was revealed that items under Social and Economic Factors with mean score of 2.76, followed by items under family background with mean score of 2.74 and items under peer influence with mean score of 2.72 were ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively. The most factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State are social and economic factors, family background and Peer Influence.

Hypotheses Testing

In this study, three null hypotheses were formulated and tested using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical procedure. Significant differences were determined at 0.05 level of significance

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State as perceived by teachers in Kwara State based on gender.*

Table 3: Means, Standard Deviations and t-value of Respondents' view on the Basis of gender

Gender	No.	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t-val.	Crit. t-val.	Decision
Male	187	40.74	3.34	398	3.31	1.96	Rejected
Female	213	40.85	3.38				

Table 3 shows the mean, standard deviation and t-value of respondents on the basis of male and female. The result on the table revealed that the calculated t-value of 3.31 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 with 398 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on gender. This implies that female reaction was higher than male reaction in respect to factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on school location.*

Table 4: ANOVA showing factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area based on school location

Sources	SS	Df	MS	Cal. val.	F- val.	Crit. F-val.	p-value	Decision
Between Group	18.52	2	9.26	.820	3.00	0.441	Accepted	
Within Group	4484.26	397	11.29					
Total	4502.79	399						

Table 4 presents the calculated F-val. of 0.820 which is less than the critical F-value of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha level. And, since the p-value of 0.441 is greater than 0.05, the hypothesis thus accepted. This implies there is no significant difference on the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on school location. It also implies that irrespective of their location, students are affected by the same factors responsible for

juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience.

Table 5: ANOVA comparing respondents on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience

Sources	SS	Df	MS	Cal. val.	F- val.	Crit. F- val.	p- value	Decision
Between Group	3.511	2	1.756	.155	3.00	0.857	Accepted	
Within Group	4499.279	397	11.333					
Total	4502.790	399						

Table 5 presents the calculated F-val. of 0.155 which is less than the critical F-value of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha level. And, since the p-value of 0.857 is greater than 0.05, thus the hypothesis was accepted. This implies there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience. It also indicates that irrespective of their years of teaching experience students are affected by the same factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Summary of the Findings

There is a significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin

Local Government Area, Oyo State based on gender

- There is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on school location
- There is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience

Discussion

Research question one stated that what are the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. It was revealed that items under Social and Economic Factors with mean score

of 2.76, followed by items under family background with mean score of 2.74 and items under peer influence with mean score of 2.72. These items were ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively. The most factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State were Social and Economic Factors, family background and peer influence in that order. Families living in poverty often face various hardships, including inadequate housing, food insecurity, and lack of access to quality education and healthcare. These conditions can create feelings of frustration, hopelessness, and alienation in adolescents, leading them to engage in delinquent behaviors such as theft or substance abuse as a means of coping.

Hypothesis one stated that *there* is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as perceived by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State *based on gender*. Thus, there is a significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on gender. This implies that female reaction was higher than male reaction in respect to factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State based on gender. This support the findings of Ogundele (2020) found that parental involvement in the academic and social development of children plays a protective role in preventing delinquency. When parents are actively engaged in their children's school activities, they can detect early signs of academic or behavioral problems and intervene before these issues escalate into more serious delinquent behavior. In contrast, a lack of parental involvement, which is often more pronounced among parents with lower educational qualifications, may leave children feeling unsupported and more likely to engage in deviant behaviors (Ogundele, 2021).

Hypothesis two stated that there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State

based on school location. This implies there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on school location. This implies that irrespective of their location students are affected by the same factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. This was in line with the findings of (Okorie, 2022) that the school environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' attitudes and behavior. A lack of effective discipline, inadequate educational resources, and poor teacher-student relationships can contribute to juvenile delinquency. In many Nigerian secondary schools, overcrowded classrooms, poorly trained teachers, and inadequate infrastructure are common challenges that create an environment conducive to disruptive behavior.

Hypothesis three stated that there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience. This implies there is no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State based on years of teaching experience. This implies that irrespective of their years of teaching experience students are affected by the same factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students as expressed by teachers in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. This corroborate the findings of Okorie (2022) indicates that parents with lower educational qualifications often have limited access to resources and may lack the necessary skills to cope with the challenges associated with parenting adolescents. Such parents may also be less able to provide a stable and structured home environment, which is crucial for the emotional and social development of children.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation

This study investigated factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State. This was to determine whether the variable of gender, school location and years of teaching experience significantly influence the scourge of juvenile delinquency in the LGA.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: the result of the findings shows that the most factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin Local Government Area, Oyo State were Social and Economic Factors, Family Background and Peer Influence. There is a significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State based on gender, however there was no significant difference on factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State based on school location and years of teaching experience.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- there should be seminar for parents enlightenment on the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State;
- there should be seminar for school administrators on how they can reduce the level factors responsible for juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Iseyin local government area, Oyo State irrespective of the years of teaching experience, gender and school location.

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